

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Assessment procedure to quantify effects of PPPs' mixtures on animals

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Milestone 6 - Assessment procedure to quantify effects of PPPs' mixtures on animals

Milestone 6 of the SPRINT project consist in the “assessment procedure to quantify effects of PPPs' mixtures on (livestock) animals”. This Milestone pertains in particular to Tier 3 (in vivo testing) of WP4.2 “Assessment of the effects of PPPs' mixtures on animal health”. As described in the SPRINT proposal, Tier 3 (in vivo testing) of WP 4.2 aims to test the top 3 individual components of concern for animals in an in vivo component-based assessment. Animal health can effectively be assessed by exposing animals to PPPs and then monitor health and performance in an experimental setup. It is a prerequisite that the experimental animal is in a phase of productive life that is sensitive to even slight suboptimal conditions. Such setup would be capable of assessing whether PPPs' exposure affects health and performance. In the SPRINT Proposal, Ross 308 chicken were considered suitable model. Ross 308 is an extremely fast-growing chicken that is vulnerable to even slight suboptimal conditions, and it is possible to conduct experiments with a high number of genetic similar animals. PPPs in the feed may be such suboptimal condition. Specifically, Milestone 6 have been addressed by the SPRINT project with the production of a detailed protocol (version 2) by the AU University for the assessment procedure to quantify effects of PPPs' mixtures on animals. Please notice that a preliminary version of the protocol (version 1) was already produced in August 2021 for D10.1 (which included all the draft protocols and procedures for animal welfare related to WP4 in vivo studies). WP10 (ethics) and the relative deliverables, including D10.1, were not present in the original proposal and were added only after the EU Commission revision of the proposal, for this reason a preliminary version of the AU protocol had to be provided in advance for that deliverable. The AU experimental protocol (version 2) is described below.

AU Experimental Protocol

Exposure of Ross 308 broiler chickens to selected pesticides

PROTOCOL VERSION: 2 (January 28, 2022)

PROJECT: SPRINT

WP: 4.2

SPONSOR: Aarhus University; Sprint; Horizon 2020

AU STUDY CODE: Not yet obtained

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I. AIMS OF THE STUDY

Based on the SPRINT tiered approach and the results from WP2 and WP4, three pesticides will be selected and tested in an experiment with chickens of a breed commonly used in commercial broiler production. Focus will be on animal performance and gut health.

II. EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

Male and female animals of the Ross 308 breed will be used. This breed is extremely fast-growing and performance is sensitive to suboptimal conditions. Pesticide exposure may be such suboptimal condition.

III. HOUSING

The chickens will be housed in 48 floor rooms (1.7 m²) at the animal facilities at Aarhus University. Straw or wood shavings will be used for bedding. Housing conditions (temperature and lighting) will follow the recommendations for Ross 308.

IV. ANIMAL MANAGEMENT

The animals will be inspected twice daily and managed by technicians with extensive experience. Personnel in charge of the management team include the principal investigator and a veterinarian with qualification and certification in animal experimentation.

V. DIET

The diet will be composed of organic ingredients and diet composition will follow the recommendations for the Ross 308 broiler as far as possible given the restraints of organic ingredients. Test compounds are mixed into the diet, or alternatively administered via drinking water.

VI. TEST SUBSTANCES, TREATMENTS AND EXPERIMENTAL PLAN

Treatments will depend on the outcome of the experiments in SPRINT WP2 and WP4 described above. With a maximum of 48 floor rooms (=replicates), the three selected pesticides can be tested individually with a single dose or they can be tested in a cocktail at three doses. This will provide 12 replicates (each of 12 animals) for each of the three treatments and the control. The animals will be exposed to the treatments upon arrival at Aarhus University as one-day old chickens. The duration of the experiment is planned to be 35 days, equivalent to the normal time to produce a Ross 308 broiler.

VII. CONDUCT OF THE STUDY

Feed intake: The daily feed intake per floor room will be recorded.

Body weight: Body weight will be recorded weekly.

Health, injuries and clinical observations: Animals will be inspected daily and deviations from normal status are recorded. The recording technician will immediately report to the principal

investigator any indication of illness or suffering. The principal investigator will then decide whether the animal should be sacrificed since no medication is normally used.

At termination of the experiment, animals will be sacrificed by CO² or intraperitoneal injection of pentobarbital/lidocaine according to an established protocol.

Gut content will be sampled and stored at -80°C until microbiota analysis.

Optional: Blood may be obtained from the jugular vein immediately before sacrifice for biochemical/biomarker analyses.

VIII. ANIMAL PERFORMANCE

Animal performance (growth and feed utilization) will be based on the recordings of feed intake and live weight.

IX. GUT MICROMIOME

Microbiome profiling will be conducted by 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing using the Illumina MiSeq platform.

X. DATA MANAGEMENT

Data management will follow the requirements of Horizon 2020. Data will be uploaded to a central platform at Aarhus University with automated backup.

XI. BIostatISTICS AND STUDY EVALUATION

Raw data will be evaluated by appropriate and generally acceptable statistical methods. Power calculation will be performed prior to performing the experiment.

XII. AMENDMENTS TO PROTOCOL

Amendments to the protocol will be filed and notified to the SPRINT coordinator and ethics committee.